

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

ClimEmpower Work Package 6, D6.8, v1

Project ClimEmpower: User Driven Climate Applications Empowering
Regional Resilience

Work package 6, Deliverable D6.8

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Deliverable details	
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10/11/2023	Draft v2	Vurnek. M (FER), inputs from partners	Final draft, ready for confirmation of all partners.
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List of Acronyms

AIT	Austrian institute of Technology GmbH (ClimEmpower Coordinator)
CC	Climate Change
CIC	Climate interaction context
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital object identifier
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts.
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
ICARIA	Improving ClimAte Resilience of critical Assets (HE project)
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation (data format)
JSON_LD	JSON for Linking Data (data format)
KISS	Keep it simple, silly
KNOWING	Framework for defining climate mitigation pathways based on understanding and integrated assessment of climate impacts, adaptation strategies and societal transformation (HE project)
MAIA	Maximising impact and accessibility of European climate research (HE Coordination Action)
MU	Mission User
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium (Standardization organisation)
PMT	Project Management Team
RA	Regional Authority
SO	Strategic Objective
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium (Standardization Organisation)
WFS	Web Feature Service (OGC Standard)
WCS	Web Coverage Service (OGC Standard)
WMS	Web Map Service (OGC Standard)
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service (OGC Standard)
XARRAY	Python package that simplifies working with labelled multi-dimensional arrays.
XML	Extensible Markup Language (Markup language standardized by W3C)

Glossary

Climate impacts	The consequences of realized risks on natural and human systems, where risks result from the interactions of climate-related hazards (including extreme weather and climate events), exposure, and vulnerability. Impacts generally refer to effects on lives; livelihoods; health and well-being; ecosystems and species; economic, social and cultural assets; services (including ecosystem services); and infrastructure (based on IPCC, 2018)
GeoServer	An open-source server for sharing geospatial data (https://geoserver.org/)
OpenAIRE	Pan-European open and sustainable scholarly communication infrastructure harvesting research output from connected data providers (https://www.openaire.eu/).
QGIS Server	QGIS Server is an open-source WMS, WFS, OGC API for Features 1.0 (WFS3) and WCS implementation that, in addition, implements advanced cartographic features for thematic mapping. (https://docs.qgis.org/)
Zenodo	a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN (https://zenodo.org/)

Executive summary

This first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) explains general policy and approach to data management in ClimEmpower. It handles the data management related issues on the administrative and technical level. This includes for example topics like data and metadata collection, publication and deposition of open data, the data repository infrastructure and compliance to the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE). The ClimEmpower Data Management Policy is explained in section 3 of this document, following the structure of the Horizon Europe DMP template. As a general guideline, ClimEmpower Data Management Policy follows three main principles:

- **KISS:** both the data management within the project and discovery, access, and reuse of data during and after the project will be made as transparent and as simple as possible.
- **FAIR:** all data used in the project shall be easily Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
- **Societally Responsible:** data produced by the project will be made publicly available unless there is a compelling ethical or commercial reason against such publication. All project outputs (e.g. data, publications, algorithms) will be explicitly checked for Ethics issues by the authors and reviewers, and the findings transparently communicated.

In addition, it includes information on methodology and standards, access and use rights, data curation and preservation.

1 ClimEmpower summary

ClimEmpower is a Horizon Europe collaborative research project dedicated to addressing the ongoing Climate Crisis in Europe by empowering the regional stakeholders in some of the most vulnerable European regions (Figure 1).

WHO

Figure 1: ClimEmpower at a glance: why, what, where, how and who.

1.1 Project context

Climate risks result from a combination of a hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. Addressing all three aspects is crucial for effective increase of regional resilience. However, exposure, vulnerability, and related aspects, such as adaptive capacity, strongly depend on available knowledge and climate literacy. Consequently, global climate crisis frequently has a higher impact on socioeconomically vulnerable regions, thanks to a higher human and economic potential for addressing the issue in more affluent regions. To maximize its impact, ClimEmpower has therefore chosen to address the EU regions featuring a combination of high potential CC impacts and low and/or stagnant regional GDP/capita. This is mainly the case for regions in South and Southeast Europe (Figure 2).

Figure 2.- aggregated potential impact of climate change (<https://www.espon.eu/climate-2012>); GDP/capita (based on <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/ddn-20210303-1>).

The context the project addresses is thus one of the ongoing global warming, high regional vulnerability, and low coping capacity of the participating regions.

The **overarching strategic objective of ClimEmpower** is to empower the Regional Authorities (RAs) and other Mission Users (MUs) in five EU-regions featuring a combination of exceptionally high climate hazards and exceptionally low coping capacity by improving their collective understanding of the Climate Change (CC) hazards, risks and resilient development pathways and supporting their knowledge-based regional planning and development through provision of relevant data, knowledge and user-defined and user-friendly decision support applications.

1.2 Project objectives

To achieve this overarching goal, **ClimEmpower has identified six SMART¹ Strategic Objectives (SO)**, each one related to one or several work packages. The SOs have also been classified according to different categories: societal, contributing to improved dialogue, awareness, cooperation and community engagement as highlighted by the European Climate Pact (SO1, SO5); scientific, corresponding to research activities for advances beyond the state of the art (SO2, SO3); technological, suggesting and/or developing novel solutions, integrating state-of-the art and digital advances (SO4); and outreach, aimed at sharing ClimEmpower results to a broader scientific and non-scientific audience, including additional regions and communities, to maximize project impact (SO6).

- SO1 Understand regional background, challenges and expectation (WP1, societal)
- SO2 Addressing the gaps in availability and usability of CC data and services (WP2 and WP4, scientific)
- SO3 Identification, definition, estimating, and communication of climate impact/resilience indicators suitable for local end-users (WP2 and WP4, scientific)
- SO4 Simplify access to CC data and development of end user applications (WP3, technological)
- SO5 Empower the regions to activate and enhance their potential for addressing the climate change challenge. (WP4, societal)
- SO6 Ensure the use and impact of the ClimEmpower outputs (WP4 and WP5, scientific and societal)

ClimEmpower’s key ambition is to **prove beyond doubt that CC-resilience should, and can, be an integral part of regional development everywhere in EU and beyond it**. That is, we anticipate that the regional stakeholders will recognise that CC-resilient development pathways offer multiple benefits to them, including but not limited to higher quality of life and reviving economy, and that these can be understood using available data, tools, and services. Second key ambition of the project is to **help the regions address the CC resilience in key community systems addressed in five ClimEmpower trials**.

Underlying philosophy of the project is to **“help the regions to help themselves”**. This will be achieved through various mechanisms, including co-creation and mediation of the regional **“Communities of Practice”**, provision of the **Climate Change -resilience training materials**, as well as in provision and training in use of the user-centric data and services – including those that have already been made available through previous research projects and EU initiatives.

¹ Specific (related to WPs), Measurable (by relevant KPIs), Achievable (the WPs in which they will be achieved are listed), Realistic (since they are referred and explained in the methodology section), and Timebound (each KPI is related to a deliverable and a month of achievement).

2 Introduction

2.1 Deliverable summary

This Deliverable is part of ClimEmpower WP6 “Project Coordination and management” and introduces the ClimEmpower Data Management policy.

2.2 Results and expected impacts

As mentioned in the Executive Summary, ClimEmpower Data Management Policy follows three main principles:

- **KISS:** both the data management within the project and discovery, access, and reuse of data during and after the project will be made as simple as possible.
- **FAIR:** all data used in the project must be easily Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
- **Societally Responsible:** data produced by the project will be made publicly available, unless there is a compelling ethical or commercial reason against such publication.

By following these principles, ClimEmpower aims to minimise the effort required for data management during and after the project, while maximising the positive societal and scientific impact of the project and minimising the potential negative side-effects on project partners and society.

2.2.1 Contribution to the project objectives

This deliverable sets up the rules and expectations for ClimEmpower outputs. It clarifies the project’s commitment to Open Data, thus primarily contributing to the strategic objectives SO2 “Addressing the gaps in availability and usability of CC data and services”, SO4 “Simplify access to CC data and development of end user applications”, and SO6 “Ensure the use and impact of the ClimEmpower outputs” (see section 1.2 for an overview of the six strategic objectives of the project).

2.2.2 Contribution to project impacts

Open and transparent ClimEmpower Data Policy will help to increase the visibility of the project results, as well as to remove the obstacles for reuse and further development of the ClimEmpower R&D results by project partners, other EU regions and by the wider R&I community.

2.3 Relation to other work

This deliverable is based on best practices in Data, Quality and Ethics management of the HE projects RESILOC, KNOWING and ICARIA. It publicly advertises the rules for transparent handling of these topics, thus complementing the Project Management Manual.

2.4 Data, security, and ethics

2.4.1 Data quality and interoperability

ClimEmpower will, as a rule, follow the best practices of the relevant science-based communities such as COPERNICUS, INSPIRE and IPCC and re-use the existing data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies for making the project data interoperable and to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines.

Relevant information on data quality and interoperability will be included in section 2.4.1 of project deliverables (this section).

2.4.2 Data accessibility, and reuse

This deliverable is the DMP and per definition does not use or produce any DMP-relevant data.

Since DMP is a first project deliverable, we have decided to publish the ClimEmpower deliverable template as the first public project output and include it in this section as an example of how this should be done.

Table 1: Other relevant outputs of ClimEmpower deliverable D6.8

Data set name	Format	Size	Owner & re-use conditions	Potential within and outside	Utility	Unique ID
ClimEmpower Deliverables_Template	DX.y .dotm	2.3MB	ClimEmopower CC-BY 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MS Word Template for ClimEmpower deliverables. Potentially useful as a starting point for developing own deliverable templates. 		10.5281/zenodo.10105210

2.4.3 Security and ethics

The work performed in this deliverable isn't considered sensitive in terms of ethics or security.

Section 3.6 of this document explicitly instructs the project participants to uphold the high ethical standards in relationship to GDPR, gender bias and societal injustice and report the findings in section 2.4.3 of the relevant deliverables.

3 ClimEmpower data management policy

By following **KISS, FAIR, and Societally Responsible Data Management principles** (outlined in Section 2), ClimEmpower aims to minimise the effort required for data management during and after the project, while maximising the positive societal and scientific impact of the project and minimising the potential negative side-effects on project partners and society.

Based on these three core principles, Data Management rules in ClimEmpower can be summarised as:

- 1) **All ClimEmpower data sets will be referenced in Zenodo**, to assure that the information is easily discoverable and can be referenced by unique DOI – during and after the project.
 - a. In particular, all Open Data that is produced in the project or published by the project for the first time will also be published in ClimEmpower community in Zenodo, under <https://zenodo.org/communities/climempower>, to assure its long-term storage through OpenAIRE.
 - b. For data that cannot be made public, e.g. due to ethical / security or commercial confidentiality concerns, the reasons for non-disclosure and conditions and procedures for accessing the data will be clearly stated in Zenodo, as well as in the relevant deliverables, and summarised in future versions of the DMP. Such data will be managed by the owner and kept for at last five years after the project end.
- 1) **All ClimEmpower deliverables published will list the data used or produced in preparation of that deliverable**, with references to data sources for input data and references to ClimEmpower Zenodo entries for data produced by the project included in section 2.4 of the document.
- 2) **A summary of this information for all deliverables will be included in updated versions of the DMP.**

3.1 Deliverable data summary

All ClimEmpower deliverables will contain a data summary in section 2.4 of the document. This summary will answer the following questions:

- 1) What existing data has been considered for reuse / used in preparation of this deliverable?
 - a. Why was a decision made to use or discard specific data sets? (if applicable)
- 2) What data has been generated in preparation of this deliverable?
 - a. Including software, key publications, and other outputs that the authors consider to be important. (if applicable)
- 3) What input and output data types and formats were used in preparation of the deliverable?
- 4) How does the data generated or re-used contribute to the objectives of the project?
- 5) Data provenance
- 6) Data size
- 7) Conditions for re-use (e.g. Open Data, Commercial License, special conditions such as commercial confidentiality or ethical constraints)
- 8) Potential utility of the data within and beyond the project.

9) Unique identifier (URI or DOI) for extended data information and access instructions.

As a rule, the data produced in the project will be published as Open Data and advertised on Zenodo, under <https://zenodo.org/communities/climempower/>, and the unique identifier will thus usually be a Zenodo DOI.

Data summary is an integral part of the ClimEmpower document template, and to be described using following tables:

Table 2: Data used in preparation of ClimEmpower deliverable DX.Y

Data set name	Format	Size	Owner & re-use conditions	Potential Utility within and outside	Unique ID
<NAME>	<FORMAT>	<SIZE>	<OWNER>, <conditions>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Summary explaining if and how this data could be useful for later work within the project and for third parties / beyond project 	Typically a DOI or URI
...				•	

Table 3: Data considered (but not used) in preparation of ClimEmpower deliverable DX.Y

Data set name	Format	Size	Owner & re-use conditions	Potential Utility within and outside	Unique ID
<NAME>	<FORMAT>	<SIZE>	<OWNER>, <conditions>	Summary explaining if and how this data could be useful for later work within the project and for third parties / beyond project	Typically a DOI or URI

Table 4: Data produced in preparation of ClimEmpower deliverable DX.Y

Data set name	Format	Size	Owner & re-use conditions	Potential Utility within and outside	Unique ID
<NAME>	<FORMAT>	<SIZE>	<OWNER>, <conditions>	Summary explaining if and how this data could be useful for later work within the project and for third parties / beyond project	Typically a DOI or URI
...					

See also section 3.3.

Other research outputs”.

3.2 FAIR data

3.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

For input data used in the project, existing unique IDs will be used when available. If no unique ID is available, ClimEmpower team will contact the data owner and request that they generate it. If nothing else works, Zenodo record for such data will be published by ClimEmpower and a DOI generated.

ClimEmpower project will introduce a project-specific channel on Zenodo and advertise all relevant data produced by the project in this channel and for each data set produced by the project, a record containing all necessary meta-information will be published. Such records will follow the standard Zenodo data model for data description and contain at least the following information:

- Dataset name.
- Human-readable description of the data (what is it, what can it be used for).
- Documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.) or a reference to such documentation.
- Reference to the project.
- Reference to partner(s) owning the data.
- Data format.
- Data size.
- Conditions for reuse: license, price, confidentiality or ethical limitations, publishing embargo date (if any).
- Instructions for data access or URI (unless the data is attached to the record)
 - Information on how to contact the data owners.
 - If necessary, also instructions on special software that is needed to read the data.
- Unique ID: either a reference to an existing unique data identifier (e.g. URI, DOI) or a new DOI generated by Zenodo.

The consortium may decide to publish such meta-information records on Zenodo also for existing data sets used in the project, e.g. if no open references are available.

3.2.2 Making data accessible

As a rule, the data produced in the project will be published as Open Data and published on Zenodo. The following exceptions are foreseen:

- If Open Data is published on a different, but equally sustainable platform or service, only a meta-information record, containing a link to actual data, will be published on Zenodo.
- Exceptions from Open Data policy can be made for commercial, ethical, legal or security reasons.

Proprietary and sensitive data used by or generated in the project will be managed by the partner owning the data / data usage rights. Project partners managing such data will keep it available on a storage of their choice (e.g., company-internal data repository) for a minimum of five years after the project end.

Partner can also request a reasonable embargo of up to six months for publishing the data, to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents). In such case, the data will be published on Zenodo with embargo date set², to assure that the data is automatically made available once the embargo end.

3.2.3 Making data interoperable

As clarified in section 2.4.1, ClimEmpower will, as a rule, follow the best practices of the relevant science-based communities such as COPERNICUS, INSPIRE and IPCC and re-use the existing data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies for making the project data interoperable and to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines.

Access to ClimEmpower geospatial data repositories and services will be established using standardised protocols such as WMS, WMTS, WFS, or WCS³. Open-source tools like GeoServer or QGIS Server will be used to implement and provide such services where appropriate.

Moreover, ClimEmpower will contribute to increased accessibility and interoperability of the data and data services within and beyond the project, through development of reusable libraries and services for climate feature extraction, data processing and indicator building. In particular, the project partner ECMWF has committed to develop a feature extraction algorithm which allows for arbitrary, non-orthogonal extraction of data from n-dimensional data cubes. This algorithm will be provided both as a web service and as a standalone library, allowing feature extraction on common data cube libraries such as “xarray”⁴.

3.2.4 Increasing data reuse

Documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.) will be provided in relevant Zenodo records – either as attached documentation, or as a reference.

As a rule, data generated in the project will be made available as Open Data to permit the widest re-use possible. Project partners can request exceptions from this rule for commercial, ethical, legal or security reasons. In addition, project partners can also request data publishing embargo, e.g., to prepare exploitation measures.

Relevant data quality assurance processes will be documented in section 2.4.1 of each deliverable (if applicable).

² „Embargo status: Users may deposit content under an embargo status and provide and end date for the embargo. The repository will restrict access to the data until the end of the embargo period; at which time, the content will become publically available automatically.“ (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>)

³ Service interfaces and data models used by ClimEmpower services will be defined in D3.1 „ClimEmpower application architecture“.

⁴ Deliverable D3.2 „Reusable libraries and services for climate feature extraction, data processing and indicator building“.

3.3 Other research outputs

No physical outputs will be generated in this project.

Other research outputs, such as software, workflows, protocols, models, reports, training materials, presentations, and publications will be managed in the same way as data. That is:

- 1) A Zenodo record will be published for each output and each relevant research output will be either attached to that Zenodo record or referenced in that record.
- 2) Relevant records will be summarized in a tabular form, analogously to the way relevant data is summarized in tables 1-3 (Table 5).

Table 5: Other relevant outputs of ClimEmpower deliverable DX.Y

Data set name	Format	Size	Owner & re-use conditions	Potential Utility within and outside	Unique ID
<NAME>	<FORMAT>	<SIZE>	<OWNER>, <conditions>	Summary explaining if and how this data could be useful for later work within the project and for third parties / beyond project	Typically a DOI or URI
...					

3.4 Allocation of resources

As explained in section 2.2, most of the ClimEmpower results will be made available as Open Data, either through Zenodo (and thus through OpenAIRE), or through some service or repository that exists independently from the project, such as the ECMWF Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S). By utilising the existing European Open Data infrastructure, the project will minimise the cost of data publication and assure long term preservation without additional costs for the project or project partners.

AIT is responsible for overseeing the overall data management in the project. However, this responsibility is partially delegated to task leaders/deliverable editors and reviewers through project manual and deliverable template, as explained in section 3.1. Since a data summary must be included in each deliverable and reviewed as a part of deliverable review, AIT will be mainly responsible to assess that requests for temporary data embargo or non-publication of data for commercial, ethical, legal or security reasons are reasonable and duly addressed. Further, AIT is responsible for combining these deliverable-level data summaries and including the results in later versions of the Data Management Plan.

Organisation and costs related to hosting the non-public project results will be carried by the partners owning the non-public results. These partners commit to managing such results for a minimum of five years after the project end.

3.5 Data security

As indicated in previous sections, most of the project data will be published as Open Data on Zenodo/OpenAIRE, or to similar platforms or services that provide reasonable guarantee of long-term sustainability. The task of assuring the long-term availability of the project results will thus be delegated to these platforms.

During the project lifetime, AIT will provide a managed data space for the whole project. This data space consists of a MS Teams group with attached data repository that can be accessed through AIT's teams and SharePoint services. Access to ClimEmpower data space is restricted to the project team and

regular backups are performed as part of the regular service maintenance. If necessary, and approved by the Project Management Team, AIT can also provide other types of data services, such as AIT-hosted project-specific GitLab repositories for the project duration.

AIT commits to keeping all project data available on a live system or as a data archive for at least 5 years after the project end.

Currently, no “secure” data spaces are foreseen at AIT. That is, sensitive data should be managed by its respective owners and should never be uploaded to the shared project data space. If necessary and approved by the Project Management Team, a separate data repository based on AIT's NextCloud can also be used for this purpose.

3.6 Ethics

ClimEmpower is aware of several potential ethical issues related to the project work. In particular:

- 1) **GDPR-related:** all private information collected during the project will be managed and used in line with the best data management practices. In particular:
 - a. All project-external participants in ClimEmpower activities such as webinars, seminars, or surveys will be presented with clear explanation of the activities prior to their participation and asked to sign informed consent forms.
 - b. Any data gathered in this way, including but not limited to photographs and video materials, will only be utilised in the scope previously defined through consent forms.
 - c. Names and contact data of the Communities of Practices members will be managed by regions participating in the project. This data will not be included in any deliverables or publications, unless explicitly agreed upon.
 - d. ClimEmpower surveys (if any) will be anonymized before utilising or publishing the data.
- 2) **Social justice and gender bias.**
 - a. All input data, algorithms and project recommendations will be explicitly assessed for potential gender bias and societal (in)justice, and the results transparently reported in section 2.4.3 of the relevant deliverables.
 - b. ClimEmpower team will discourage use of such data, algorithms, and mitigation/adaptation recommendations to the maximal possible extent and in favour of ethically sound alternatives.

As of November 2023, there are no other known ethic or legal issues impacting the data sharing in ClimEmpower. Ethics will be explicitly assessed for all data used or produced in the project and transparently communicated in section 2.4.3 of the relevant deliverables.

3.7 Other issues

As of November 2023, it is not foreseen to make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.

4 ClimEmpower data summary

This deliverable is the first public deliverable of the project. Consequently, no data relevant to this Data Management Plan has been published so far. Following table provides an overview of all the planned public deliverables and their anticipated relevance for the future versions of the DMP. Minus indicates that no relevance is anticipated, question mark indicates that relevance is currently unclear, + indicates medium and ++ high anticipated relevance level.

Table 6: Public deliverables of ClimEmpower, their due dates and anticipated DMP relevance

Deliverable No.	Deliverable name	Due Date	Interoperability relevance?	Data relevance?	Security and ethics relevance?
D1.2	ClimEmpower scenarios	31 May 2024	+	+	++
D2.1	Climate Change resilience: identified data, services, and gaps	31 May 2024	+	+	++
D2.2	Climate Change resilience: indicators	30 Nov 2024	+	?	++
D2.3	Downscaling and data fusion for Climate Change resilience	30 Nov 2024	?	+	?
D2.4	Measures and strategies for increased Climate Change resilience	31 May 2025	?	?	+
D3.1	ClimEmpower application architecture	31 Aug 2024	++	+	?
D3.2	Reusable libraries and services for climate feature extraction, data processing and indicator building	31 Aug 2025	++	++	?
D3.3	HTML5 framework and user-centric applications for climate resilience	31 May 2026	?	?	?
D4.1	Educational materials for increased regional CC-resilience v1	31 Aug 2024	?	?	+
D4.2	Educational materials for increased regional CC-resilience v2	28 Feb 2026	?	?	+
D4.3	Regional CC-resilience recommendations v1	28 Feb 2025	?	?	+
D4.4	Regional CC-resilience recommendations v2	31 May 2026	?	?	+
D4.5	ClimEmpower application and trial specifications	31 Aug 2025	?	+	?
D4.6	Community testing and validation report	31 Aug 2026	?	?	+
D5.1	Project Web site	29 Feb 2024	-	-	?

Deliverable No.	Deliverable name	Due Date	Interoperability relevance?	Data relevance?	Security and ethics relevance?
D5.2	Dissemination communication plan v1 and	29 Feb 2024	?	?	?
D5.3	Dissemination communication plan v2 and	28 Feb 2025	?	?	?
D5.4	Dissemination communication plan v3 and	31 Aug 2026	?	?	?
D5.5	ClimEmpower dissemination materials	31 May 2026	?	?	?
D5.6	Stakeholders' engagement plan and events reports v1	31 May 2024	+	+	+
D5.7	Stakeholders' engagement plan and events reports v2	28 Feb 2025	+	+	+
D5.8	Stakeholders' engagement plan and events reports v3	31 Aug 2026	+	+	+
D6.8	Data Management Plan v1	30 Nov 2023	+	+	+
D6.9	Data Management Plan v2	31 May 2026	+	+	+

4.1 Dx.y DPM report template

Following information will be extracted from all future (public) deliverables of the project and integrated in future versions of the DMP.

4.1.1 Contribution to the project objectives

4.1.2 Contribution to project impacts

4.1.3 Data quality and interoperability

4.1.4 Data accessibility, and reuse

4.1.5 Security and ethics

4.2 D6.8 Data Management Plan v1

Since D6.8 is the first project deliverable, we have decided to use it to demonstrate how the DMP report template will be filled in. All the text below is extracted from the section 2 of D6.8 (this document).

- Delivery date: November 2023
- Data management plan does not per-se produce any data, but for the sake of demonstration, we decided to publish the Deliverable Template on Zenodo.
- The work performed in this deliverable isn't considered sensitive in terms of ethics or security.

4.2.1 Contribution to the project objectives

This deliverable sets up the rules and expectations for ClimEmpower outputs. It clarifies the project’s commitment to Open Data, thus primarily contributing to the strategic objectives SO2 “Addressing the gaps in availability and usability of CC data and services”, SO4 “Simplify access to CC data and development of end user applications”, and SO6 “Ensure the use and impact of the ClimEmpower outputs”.

4.2.2 Contribution to project impacts

Open and transparent ClimEmpower Data Policy will help to increase the visibility of the project results, as well as to remove the obstacles for reuse and further development of the ClimEmpower R&D results by project partners, other EU regions and by the wider R&I community.

4.2.3 Data quality and interoperability

ClimEmpower will, as a rule, follow the best practices of the relevant science-based communities such as COPERNICUS, INSPIRE and IPCC and re-use the existing data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies for making the project data interoperable and to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines.

4.2.4 Data accessibility, and reuse

This deliverable is the DMP and per definition does not use or produce any DMP-relevant data.

Since DMP is a first project deliverable, we have decided to publish the ClimEmpower deliverable template as the first public project output and include it in D6.8 as an example of how this should be done.

Table 7: Other relevant outputs of ClimEmpower deliverable D6.8

Data set name	Format	Size	Owner & re-use conditions	Potential within and outside	Utility	Unique ID
ClimEmpower Deliverables_Template	DX.y .dotm	2.3MB	ClimEmpower CC-BY 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MS Word Template for ClimEmpower deliverables. Potentially useful as a starting point for developing own deliverable templates. 		10.5281/zenodo.10105210

4.2.5 Security and ethics

The work performed in this deliverable isn’t considered sensitive in terms of ethics or security.

Document explicitly instructs the project participants to uphold the high ethical standards in relationship to GDPR, gender bias and societal injustice and report the findings in section 2.4.3 of the relevant deliverables.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the ClimEmpower Data Management Principles and Procedures. ClimEmpower DMP follows three main principles:

- **KISS:** both the data management within the project and discovery, access, and reuse of data during and after the project will be made as simple as possible.
- **FAIR:** all data used in the project must be easily Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
- **Societally Responsible:** data produced by the project will be made publicly available unless there is a compelling ethical or commercial reason against such publication.

KISS principle is mainly enforced by delegating the task of indicating which data has been assessed, used, or produced in the project to the tasks where such data is produced or used, and by integrating the quality control thereof in overall deliverable reviewing process.

FAIRness is mainly achieved by publishing all meta-information on data produced in the project on Zenodo and, as a rule, publishing all data produced in the project as Open Data – either attached to Zenodo record or in a separate Open Data service or repository whose long-term existence is assured independently from the project.

Finally, societal responsibility is achieved by providing a mechanism for assessing the commercial, ethical, legal or security reasons against data publication for each ClimEmpower deliverable and transparently communicating the findings in the “Data Summary” Section 2.4 Data, security, and ethics of each deliverable.

For the sake of demonstration, these deliverable self-references its own “DMP-relevant information”, from sections 2.2 and 2.4, in the section 4.2 of the document.